

COMPUTATIONAL MODELS AND VARIATIONAL FORMULATIONS FOR LAMINATED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Different intentions in the analysis of laminated structures require different models some of which are screened in the present paper. The attention is particularly focused on special aspects of two-dimensional approximations used in laminated composites, such as type of kinematical hypothesis, geometrical and physical relations. Then, various variational formulations are presented, beginning from the Hu-Washizu functional. They include also the description of the delamination phenomena presented here in the form of unilateral boundary conditions. The paper ends up with numerical examples demonstrating the influence of various 2-D approximations on the deflections and buckling loads for hemispherical shells under external pressure.

Keywords: two-dimensional approximations, variational formulations, delamination, hemispherical shells, buckling

1. INTRODUCTION

Laminated composites are versatile materials suitable for a wide variety of structures. In a direct correspondence with its applications and foreseen in advance possible failure modes, various computational models must be applied. It remains the responsibility of the designer to decide which model he needs. Profound expertise concerning the material behaviour as well as the scope of the different models is a precondition for a satisfactory selection. The requirement to keep the computational effort as low as possible always contradicts the desired extent and accuracy of the results.

Generally, for thinwalled structures, both isotropic and anisotropic, 2-D approximations are employed and extensively examined in order to avoid more complicated and computer time consuming 3-D models. For laminated thinwalled structures the use of 3-D models is limited to a special cases only, for instance to investigate free edge effects and similar problems. Thus, in the applied 2-D models of laminated structures the primer and most important problem closes in the proper choice of the used approximations.

2. FUNDAMENTAL RELATIONS

The analysis of laminated structures may be carried out at two different levels: at the level of a laminate or at the level of a layer (narrower than the previous). The decision which of two

approaches will be employed depends rather on the type of failure modes that we are looking for. For instance the global behaviour of structure, such as deflections or buckling may be described in a rather good manner at the level of the laminate. However, such phenomena as ply failure, delamination etc. require more precise investigations at the level of the layer. At the both levels of the analysis the proper (ie. the most accurate) description of failure modes bases on three factors: the form of the kinematical hypothesis, the type of geometrical relations and the modeling of strain-stress relations for composite materials (physical law). These three factors commonly with boundary and subsidiary conditions lead to the variational formulation of the problem. Then, the discretization of the functional with the use of appropriate numerical schemes allows to obtain the field of required solutions.

For shells treated as 3-D bodies the basic equations are reduced via assumptions on the displacement field (kinematical hypothesis) to 2-D equations. In general, the 3-D displacement vector $u_\alpha^{(k)}(x, y, z)$ can be written in the following form:

$$u_\alpha^{(k)}(x, y, z) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} U_{j\alpha}^{(k)}(x, y) \Phi_{j\alpha}^{(k)}(z), \quad \alpha = 1, 2, 3 \quad (1)$$

According to the above representation of 3-D displacements 2-D models of laminated thinwalled structures can be grouped into two broad categories: $k=0$ corresponds to laminatewise models (at the level of the laminate) and includes transverse shear theories of the j th order and as $k=1, 2, \dots, N$ one can obtain layerwise models (at the level of the layer). N denotes the total number of layers in the laminate. For the second group the relation (1) is in fact the set of k equations and each of them describes the distributions of displacements along the z coordinate in one layer only, ie. for $z \in [z_{k-1}, z_k]$. $\Phi_{j\alpha}^{(k)}(z)$ usually are polynomials or trigonometric functions. The total number of independent functional degrees of freedom $U_{j\alpha}^{(k)}(x, y)$ is completely free.

Table 1. Number of parameters used in the description of composite shells deformations

Variants of kinematical hypothesis	Level of the layer		Level of the laminate
	Generally	Kinematical contact conditions	
Compressibility of the normal element	6N	3N+3	6
First order shear theory	5N	2N+3	5
Love-Kirchhoff's hypothesis	3N	—	3

Table 1 shows the variants of the shell theories corresponding to various number of the independent functions $U_{j\alpha}$. As it may be seen the second column in the table has been obtained with the use of subsidiary conditions at the interfaces between the layers expressing simply kinematical contact conditions at $z=z_l$ and written in the following form:

$$u_\alpha^{(k)}(x, y, z_l) = u_\alpha^{(k-1)}(x, y, z_l) \quad (2)$$

At the level of the layer the next step toward the reduction of unknown functions $U_{j\alpha}$ leads to the use of transverse shear and normal stress continuity conditions at the interfaces:

$$\sigma_{\alpha 3}^{(k)}(x, y, z_l) = \sigma_{\alpha 3}^{(k-1)}(x, y, z_l), \quad \alpha = 1, 2, 3 \quad (3)$$

After elimination with the use of eqns (2),(3), the formulation (1) at the level of layer ends up with the identical number of unknown functions $U_{j\alpha}$ as at the level of laminate - the last column

in Table 1 (excluding Love-Kirchhoff's shell theory, of course).

At the both levels of the analysis (ie. of the laminate or of the layer) eqn (1) may be supplemented by an additional set of subsidiary conditions relating to the behaviour of displacements or strains at the top and bottom surfaces of the laminate or of the individual layers in the laminate. This procedure tends also to the reduction of the total number of functional degrees of freedom $U_{j\alpha}^{(k)}(x, y)$. In general, three additional constraints are commonly introduced here. They may be written in the following form:

$$L(U_{r\alpha}^{(k)}(x, y)\Phi_{r\alpha}^{(k)}(z)) = F\left(\sum_{j=1}^{r-1}(U_{j\alpha}^{(k)}(x, y)\Phi_{j\alpha}^{(k)}(z))\right), \quad \alpha = 1, 2, 3 \quad (4)$$

L means linear differential operator and F denotes function or integral operator. It should be emphasized here that the above additional constraints are mainly introduced in higher order transverse shear theories, so that in practice the total number of additional constraints reduces to two only. In addition, they are mainly applied at the level of the laminate (ie. $k=0$). The relations (5) have the strict physical sense and for instance Reddy [1] used the condition of vanishing shear strains at the top and bottom surfaces of the laminate, Murthy [2] introduced mean rotations, whereas Kwon and Akin [3] eliminated shear stresses at the upper and lower surfaces.

In literature, the majority of works ends up the expansion in eqn (1) at cubic terms in functions $\Phi_{j\alpha}^{(k)}(z)$ (ie. $j \leq 3$) due to the computational effort required for a solution as j increases. In addition, the analysis is mainly carried out at the level of the laminate ($k=0$). In the second possible approach - at the level of the layer ($k > 0$), the authors of numerous works develop theories basing on linear with respect to z variable form of the functions $\Phi_{j\alpha}^{(k)}(z)$. Discrete layerwise cubic displacement functions were used for instance by Whitney [4], but such an approximations of the Φ functions is introduced very rarely.

As it may be seen with the use of relations (1)-(5) an unlimited number of various shell hypothesis and in this way of shell theories may be constructed. However, it is necessary to compare always the accuracy of solutions versus computational effort.

It is worth to mention also that Reddy [5] has given a generalized description comprising both levels of the analysis, ie. laminate and layer. Babuska et al. [6] propose completely different approach to the analysis of thinwalled laminated structures basing on the sequence of hierarchical models.

The next crucial point in the rigorous analysis of laminated structures deals with the assumptions concerning with strain (or stress) measures and the used description, ie. a Lagrangian (updated or total) or an Eulerian. Such a decision allows to describe in an accurate way (if it is necessary) large deformations and nonlinear behaviour of laminates. From the point of view of both finite element applications and large deformation studies the Lagrangian description is rather commonly used in the analysis.

Let us begin our considerations from the case of large strain analysis which can be used in the description of laminated shells behaviour via degenerated 3-D finite elements. Since the analysis is nonlinear the best idea is to employ herein Hill's [7] constitutive relations of rate dependent material (in the updated Lagrangian formulation) in the following form:

$$\Delta S_{\alpha\beta} = C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} D_{\gamma\delta} \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta S_{\alpha\beta}$ is Jaumann (co-rotational) rate of the Kirchhoff stress, $C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$ means stiffness matrix and the last term:

$$D_{\gamma\delta} = \frac{1}{2}(\Delta u_{\gamma,\delta} + \Delta u_{\delta,\gamma}) \quad (6)$$

means rate of deformation tensor. Inserting (1) to (6) one can determine the necessary number of d.o.f. per node expressed here by the unknown functions $U_{j\alpha}^{(k)}(x, y)$.

The total Lagrangian formulation is rather applied in the description of axisymmetric structures and is an extension of Reissner's shell theory. In this case the geometrical relations are derived with the help of pure geometrical transformations and are commonly expressed in the convenient terms of the stretch ratios. The broader discussion of those problems is presented eg. by Taber [8]. However, it is interesting to mention here that Taber's proposal of asymptotic expansions leads almost directly to the Babuska et al. [6] hierarchical model.

The next step toward the reduction of geometrical relations tends to the application of shell theories taking into account small strains only. We would like to present here one of many versions, extensively investigated eg. by Palmerio et al. [9]. It deals with shells undergoing large deflections but moderate rotations of the normal to a midsurface. In this case the strain tensor components are expressed in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{\alpha\beta} &= \epsilon_{\alpha\beta} + \frac{1}{2}\omega_{\delta\alpha}\omega_{,\beta}^{\delta} + \frac{1}{2}(\epsilon_{\delta\beta}\omega_{,\alpha}^{\delta} + \epsilon_{\delta\alpha}\omega_{,\beta}^{\delta}) + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon_{\delta\alpha}\epsilon_{,\beta}^{\delta}, \quad \epsilon_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{2}(\bar{u}_{\alpha;\beta} + \bar{u}_{\beta;\alpha}), \\ \omega_{\alpha\beta} &= \frac{1}{2}(\bar{u}_{\alpha;\beta} - \bar{u}_{\beta;\alpha}), \quad \bar{u}_{i;j} = c_i^l(u_{l;j} - b_{lj}u_3), \quad \bar{u}_{i;3} = c_i^l u_{l;3}, \quad \bar{u}_{3;j} = u_{3;j} + b_j^l u_l, \quad \bar{u}_{3;3} = u_{3,3} \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

Substituting (1) into (7) we find the expressions for the unknown functions $U_{j\alpha}^{(k)}(x, y)$. The next simplification of geometrical relations leads to the elimination of all nonlinear terms in eqn (7) and confines the class of the considered problems to the analysis of small strains and deflections. As it may be noticed the type of possible geometrical relations enlarges again (in the connection with the types of possible kinematical hypothesis) the class of various shell theories which may be applied in the analysis.

The next vast group of problems in the area of laminated structures concerns definitions of the stiffness matrix. First of all it should be emphasized that the prediction of homogenized elastic moduli from fibre and matrix properties occupies most of the scientific attention in the micromechanical field. Homogenization is probably the proper and most effective way to overcome the difficulties with the fibre and matrix models. However, it should be clearly pointed out that independently on the assumed homogenized models of 3-D composite bodies further assumptions are required mainly due to the form of kinematical hypothesis (1) taken into account. Generally, for anisotropic materials the stiffness matrix is characterized by 21 material constants. The assumption of the material symmetry with respect to three planes reduces this number to 9 for 3-D bodies. If in the composite materials one of the planes possess isotropic properties the number of independent material constants decreases to 5 (transversely orthotropic bodies). In most cases 3-D body is approximated with the use of the hypothesis (1) to 2-D problem. Therefore, 3-D body is treated as 2-D orthotropic one (4 independent material constants) but the appearing inconsistencies in the description (discontinuities in shear stresses at the layer interfaces), especially at the level of the laminate are diminished by the introduction of additional constants taking into account variations in the composite topology (stacking sequences, fibre orientations etc.). Various approaches in this area are summarized in Table 2. As it may be seen the second column in Table 2 includes fibre orientations θ_k as the material constant. It indicates simply the fact that the terms in the stiffness matrix at the level of the laminate arise by the transformation from the local (material) to global (surface) coordinate system and then by the integration over the thickness of the laminate (in the classical sense) analogous to that for isotropic thinwalled structures. Let us notice that the second and third row in the Table 2 contain the shear correction factors k_{13} and k_{23} representing the influence of the transverse shear effects and generally they vary with stacking sequences and property relations. They are determined by considering an orthotropic laminate subjected to cylindrical

bending as suggested by Whitney[10]. One can adopt also Reissner's approach here which leads to a constant reduction factor identical to that for homogeneous isotropic plates. Poisson's ratios are not listed in Table 2. In summary, one can state that for 2-D modeling of laminated composites the form of the stiffness matrix is directly connected with the assumptions dealing with the kinematical hypothesis (the number of material constants) and then with additional assumptions concerning the stress distributions along the shell thickness. Therefore, one can state that the problem of proper physical relations and their definitions do not require any particular computational efforts.

Table 2. Material constants for 2-D laminated structures

Variants of the analysis	Material constants	
	Level of the laminate	Level of the layer
L-K shell theory	$E_1, E_2, G_{12}, \theta_k$	—
Transverse shear theories	$E_1, E_2, G_{12}, k_{13} G_{13}, k_{23} G_{23}, \theta_k$ ($k_{13} = k_{23} = \frac{5}{6}$)	$E_1, E_2, G_{12}, k_{13} G_{13}, k_{23} G_{23}$ ($k_{13} = k_{23} = \frac{5}{6}$)
Compressibility of the normal	$E_1, E_2, E_3, G_{12}, k_{13} G_{13}, k_{23} G_{23}, \theta_k$ ($k_{13} = k_{23} = \frac{5}{6}$)	$E_1, E_2, E_3, G_{12}, k_{13} G_{13}, k_{23} G_{23}$ ($k_{13} = k_{23} = \frac{5}{6}$)

3. VARIATIONAL FORMULATIONS FOR LAMINATED STRUCTURES

The laminated structure represents 3-D body and occupies the space $V = \Omega \times [-t/2, t/2] = \cup V^{(k)}$, where $V^{(k)}$ is a space occupied by the individual layer. Let us assume that the z axis means the axis perpendicular to each layers in local coordinate systems and it allows to introduce one global z axis for each plies in the laminate. At the level of the layer the total boundary may be decomposed into the following parts: the surface S being the boundary of the space V (ie. $\partial V = S$) and $N-1$ contact surfaces $S^{(k,k+1)}$ of the neighbourhood layers (ie. $S^{(k,k+1)} = V^{(k)} \cap V^{(k+1)}$). Thus, the total boundary consists of two different parts which are directly connected with the prescribed types of boundary conditions. On the surface S the classical b.c. (in the form of equalities) are defined (so-called bilateral b.c.) and they determine values of the displacement field W_α and (or) the distributed external loads s_α :

$$\sigma_{\alpha\beta}^{(k)} n_\beta^{(k)} = s_\alpha, \quad u_{j\alpha}^{(k)} = W_{j\alpha} \text{ on } S, \quad k = 1 \text{ or } k = N \quad (8)$$

The second type of b.c. relates to the behaviour and possible failure modes of the individual layers in the laminate. As the bonding between two neighbourhood layers is perfect on the surfaces $S^{(k,k+1)}$ at least the condition (2) should be satisfied (or (3)). In the opposite case delamination failure mode occurs at interfaces of each individual ply in the laminate. In the last few years Kim and Soni [11] conducted many studies to investigate the onset of delamination and demonstrated with conclusive evidence, both experimentally and theoretically that delamination failure is stimulated by the interlaminar normal and shear stress components. Thus, the initiation, development and possible further closure of delamination may be expressed via unilateral b.c. (formulated in the form of inequalities) and written in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{if } \sigma_{\alpha 3}^{(k)} < Z_{\alpha 3} \text{ then (2) is satisfied} \\ & \text{if } \sigma_{\alpha 3}^{(k)} \geq Z_{\alpha 3} \text{ then } u_\alpha^{(k)}(x, y, z_l) > u_\alpha^{(k-1)}(x, y, z_l) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Let us note also that similar formulation with the use of u.b.c may be applied to the study of FPF in the sense of the limit (strain or stresses) theories.

Thus, physical relations (5), geometrical equations (7), bilateral (8) and unilateral (9) b.c. form a complete set of equations which is generally used in looking for any static solutions at the level of the layer. However, in this case the analysis (due to the form of equations (7)) is limited to the theory including into considerations small strains only. The above mentioned relations are the starting point to the variational formulation of the problem. In general, the functional describing laminated structures J can be divided into three parts:

$$J = J_{en} + J_{bbc} + J_{ubc} \quad (10)$$

where the first part corresponds to the internal energy, the second to all b.c. formulated in the equality form and the third to takes into account the influence of the unilateral b.c. The basic approaches used for laminated structures are summarized and presented in the matrix form in Table 3.

Table 3.

Hu-Washizu $J = J(\sigma, \mathbf{e}, \mathbf{u})$	
$J_{en}(\sigma, \mathbf{e}, \mathbf{u}) = \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{V^{(k)}} \left(\frac{1}{2} [e^{(k)}]^{Tr} [C^{(k)}] [e^{(k)}] - [\sigma^{(k)}]^{Tr} [e^{(k)}] + [\sigma^{(k)}]^{Tr} [e^{(k)}(u_\alpha^{(k)})] \right) dV$	
$J_{bbc} = - \int_S ([\sigma^{(k)} \cdot n^{(k)}]^{Tr} [u - W] + [s]^{Tr} [u]) dS$	$J_{ubc} = - \sum_{l=1}^{N-1} \left(\int_{S^{(l,l+1)}} [u^{(l)} - u^{(l+1)}] [\sigma_3^{(l,l+1)}] dS \right)$
Hellinger-Reissner $J = J(\sigma, \mathbf{u})$	
$J_{en}(\sigma, \mathbf{u}) = \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{V^{(k)}} \left(-\frac{1}{2} [\sigma^{(k)}]^{Tr} [(C^{(k)})^{-1}]^{Tr} [\sigma^{(k)}] + [\sigma^{(k)}]^{Tr} [e^{(k)}(u_\alpha^{(k)})] \right) dV$	
$J_{bbc} = \int_S ([\sigma^{(k)} \cdot n^{(k)}]^{Tr} [u + W] - [s]^{Tr} [u]) dS$	$J_{ubc} = \sum_{l=1}^{N-1} \left(\int_{S^{(l,l+1)}} [u^{(l)} - u^{(l+1)}] [\sigma_3^{(l,l+1)}] dS \right)$
Lagrange $J = J(\mathbf{u}, \lambda)$	
$J_{en}(\mathbf{u}) = \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{V^{(k)}} \left(\frac{1}{2} [e^{(k)}(u_{\alpha lpha}^{(k)})]^{Tr} [C^{(k)}] [e^{(k)}(u_\alpha^{(k)})] \right) dV$	
$J_{bbc} = - \int_S ([\lambda]^{Tr} [u - W] + [s]^{Tr} [u]) dS$	$J_{ubc} = - \sum_{l=1}^{N-1} \left(\int_{S^{(l,l+1)}} [u^{(l)} - u^{(l+1)}] [\lambda] dS \right)$

where

$$[\sigma_3^{(l,l+1)}] = [(\sigma^{(l)} - \sigma^{(l+1)}) \cdot n_3] \quad (11)$$

Variations of all variables being the arguments of the functionals lead directly to the equations of equilibrium, boundary conditions and geometrical relations in the case of the Hu-Washizu approach. It is worth to mention that in the case of perfect bonding between the layers ((2) and (3) are satisfied) the variational principle is formulated in the form of equality:

$$\delta J = 0 \quad (12)$$

whereas in the case of the delamination failure (unilateral b.c.):

$$J(r^{*(k)} - r^{(k)}) \geq 0, \quad \forall r^{*(k)} \in R^* \quad (13)$$

$r^{*(k)}$ denotes the field of kinematically admissible solutions, i.e. satisfying geometrical relations, equilibrium equations and b.b.c. and represents variables being the arguments of the analyzed functional. However, the presented above variational formulations are rather rarely used in the analysis of laminated structures, mainly in the approaches applying degenerated 3-D FE. The most commonly used method of the solution bases on the integration over the structure thickness and reducing of the initial space V (or $V^{(k)}$) to the 2-D space Ω . In this case, all statical variables are replaced by the vector of stress resultants $[P]$ defined in the following way:

$$[P^{(k)}] = \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \sigma_{\alpha\beta}^{(k)} [z] dz, \quad [z] = (1, z, z^2, z^3, \dots), \quad \alpha, \beta = 1, 2, 3 \quad (14)$$

By the analytical inverse transformation to (9) and with the use of eqn (1) one can express each component of the stress field $\sigma_{\alpha\beta}^{(k)}$ as the linear function f of the stress resultants $[P^{(k)}]$ and an algebraic function of the z coordinate:

$$\sigma_{\alpha\beta}^{(k)} = f_{\alpha\beta}^{(k)}([P^{(k)}]; z), \quad \alpha, \beta = 1, 2, 3 \quad (15)$$

Each component of the vector $[P^{(k)}]$ is conjugated to the component of strain vector $[\epsilon^{(k)}]$

$$[\epsilon^{(k)}] = \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} e_{\alpha\beta}[z] dz, [z] = (1, z, z^2, z^3, \dots), \alpha, \beta = 1, 2, 3 \quad (16)$$

via the stiffness matrix $[C^{(k)}]$,

$$[P^{(k)}] = [C^{(k)}][\epsilon^{(k)}] \quad (17)$$

The dimensions of the matrices $[P^{(k)}]$, $[C^{(k)}]$ and $[\epsilon^{(k)}]$ depends only on the number of generalized functions $U_{j\alpha}^{(k)}(x, y)$ assumed in eqn (1), whereas their explicit form on the form of geometrical relations (7) and the stiffness matrix for 3-D bodies, for instance one of the presented in Table 2. As it may be seen the presented above definitions deals with the analysis at the level of the layer. One may obtain the same relations at the level of the laminate inserting $k=0$ and replacing z_{k-1} (z_k) by $-t/2$ ($t/2$, resp.). However, in the latter case it is impossible to introduce directly the conditions (2) or (3) or u.b.c. In order to avoid it one may introduce sublaminates and so-called global-local approach but it does not eliminate the discontinuities in transverse shear stresses.

4. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

The author has performed comparative studies with some shell theories using the numerical 3-D solutions as a yardstick. The analysis have been carried out for hemispherical shells made of unidirectional CFRP

$$E_1 = 203 \text{ GPa}, E_2 = 11.2 \text{ GPa}, E_3 = 0.1 E_2, G_{12} = 8.4 \text{ GPa}, G_{13} = 0.6 G_{12}, G_{23} = 0.4 G_{12}, \nu_{12} = 0.32, \nu_{13} = 0.45 \quad (18)$$

clamped at edges and subjected to the external pressure q . It goes without saying that the Kirchhoff-Love shell theory holds for very thin shells. Thicker shells are better described by the higher order shell theories but they suffer from an increased effort required for the solution.

Fig.2 presents the influence of the shell theories on the buckling loads for the analysed structure. As it may be seen transverse shear effects reduce significantly buckling pressures. The reduction factor depends entirely on the type of theory used in considerations and on the type of the stiffness matrix. However, it seems that in the analyzed case that the constant transverse shear factor $k=5/6$ gives sufficiently accurate results in the comparison with transverse shear shell theory incorporating variable shear factors k_{13}, k_{23} even for moderately thick shells. The use of Kirchhoff-Love shell theory enables to find upper bounds of buckling pressures only.

Acknowledgements

The support from the KBN grant PB-899/3/91 is gratefully acknowledged.

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